

The Main Reason that Thailand's High School Students are Not Adapting in the English Language

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ABSTRACT

A large majority of high school students in Thailand have obstacles with the utilization of the English language; however, they have set their goal to be good at English. More than that, many students are intending and wanting to be even more successful in English. The objectives research regarding of a study of the main reasons why high school students in Thailand do not specialize in English were: (1) finding reasons they are not adapted and be good at English, (2) searching the reason why Thailand's children defected of learning English languages, (3) providing plausible and reasonable solutions for students. The instrument used in this study was a questionnaire survey of 130 high school students from the various schools which information has been collected by using statistical analysis in terms of turning to be the percentage. Following, each of percentage values has been arranged into categories before finding the best solutions to assist the high school students. It follows that responses from Thai high school students who think they are average and below average are 55.4% and 23% respectively. As well as skills, Speaking is the weakest skill which has a variety of causes which half of responses are inexperienced; furthermore, the other answers such as being too afraid of speaking and unknowing vocabulary are factors which make inefficient improvement in speaking skill. Consequently, 49.2 percent of students think complexity of grammatical range and accuracy is difficult.

Keywords: English, Language, High school, Education

INTRODUCTION

English is a universal language and knowing how to communicate in English language is essential regarding anyone who is seeking to succeed in countless fields. Furthermore, English is the language of science, computers, tourism, etc. (CTN News, January 14, 2020). Knowing it increases your chances of getting a job in a multinational company in-country or abroad, it is internationally acknowledged in the global workforce. Besides, learning English also gives you greater access to better cultural understanding.

Nowadays, English has been accepted to be the international language. Definitely, Thailand has prepared English subjects for the student to study (Noom-ura, 2013). It is a general norm in this present day that students aged become the main priority to study and learn. Mainly thanks to that, most of them feel uncomfortable and do not understand the real reason in the light of studying in some subjects, which high school students in Thailand prefer the other subjects to English; nevertheless, this wrong mindset is still not been solving by anyone with more serious (Mr. Diden Benhawan, 2012). Since everyone wants to be great at English; therefore, we have compiled a problem from high school students in

Thailand in terms of finding out the reason why the ways of learning English in Thailand should be solved as quickly as possible.

Moreover, this research was collected from 130 students' responses which contained various types of questionnaires along with opportunities to commend other advice. For example, which skills of English language (i.e. listening, speaking, reading, and writing) do high school students think are the most difficult and how do they handle this problem? (Sunisa Sasum1 and Bruce Weeks Faculty of International Business, 2018) Because the researchers are also a high school student, we are able to be more understandable in those fundamental causes of the problem (Jefferson, 2013).

This study found the true reason why Thai high school students are not good at English, to study the defects of Thailand's High School Students in English language and provide correct solutions to students.

METHODOLOGY

The quantitative questionnaire was used in this research by collecting the data from 130 high school students in various programs and schools in Thailand. Also, the research selected the sample from an online questionnaire by providing a link on social media. These survey questions include fundamental questions such as gender, grade, learning program together with viewpoints toward English in Thailand's high school curriculum. To analyze the truth of the data, the researcher created questions about the main problem in the English language of high school students in Thailand. The analysis of data regarding both descriptive and inferential statistics was achieved from 130 high school students' responses. Those questions include various types of choices such as the rate of satisfaction, part of English skills, level of their own respondent's English abilities, and others. For example, the first question is if you are interested in English and how you feel, whether you are interested or not, but

almost of the 130 children or 81 percent from all of the responders felt satisfied with learning English. Secondly, do you have any hobbies to improve English skills such as listening to music, watching movies or reading various books? The result is 82.3 percent of Thailand's High school students have English activities to do in their leisure time. Following with question three, have you ever engaged in English language activities? some people have been and some may have not. However, most of the children answered that they used to have 86.2 percent. Question four: what is your English level, least, medium, good, or excellent? The answer that came first was medium as 72 students out of 130 students. The second was good at which is 27 students answering and the third ranking is the least that 26 people, the least and the excellent descending order. Focusing more on question five, what skills do you think you are weak in English, such as listening, speaking, reading, writing? 130 students in Thailand have chosen to speak 55 people, writing 48, listening 16, and reading 11. Why is it that weakens those skills as the sixth question which many children answer that they cannot understand and cannot understand when some people have conversations with them. Next, the seventh question is what do you think is the reason for your weak English? The answer is grammar and word ranges are the main cause of them all? The cause of this may be because they themselves do not dare to act. There is no foundation from the beginning and the vocabulary is too difficult. The last question these Thai children ask is What do you think the solution should be? The answer is all in one voice: Everyone must be more open-minded and trained for themselves. Finally, this research will indicate the relationship between high school students' weakness or strength in English and the main causes of those problems.

RESULT

In this research, there are a total of 130 people who have joined which include about 85 females and 45 males. Surprisingly, 81 people are studying in grade 12 as the highest proportion while there are around 31 people who are studying in grade 11. Turning to look at the smallest part, there are only 18 who are coming from grade 10. In Thailand, after graduating from grade 9, all of the students will be separated in various types of programs by taking each of the student's favor and their own choices in mind. This turning point of Thai students has significant effects since it relates to the major of faculty in university. Thanks to those supported ideas, the researcher team would like to take student's programs into consideration too. This survey questionnaire indicates that there are about 77 people from the Sciences - Mathematics Program, 21 of students are studying in Mathematics - Arts Program, 25 people in Language - Arts Program and 7 people from other programs.

Table 1 : How much high school students are interested in English.

Choice	Frequency	Percent
Satisfied	106	81.5
Neutral	1	0.8
Dissatisfied	23	17.7

Table 2 : Thailand's high School students' attitude on their English Level

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Well above average	1	0.8
Above average	27	20.8
Average	72	55.4
Below average	26	20
Well below average	4	3

Table 1 shows the number of high school students in Thailand who are interested in English language. It is 106 people of 81.5

percent Satisfied in the English language, only 1 person of 0.8 percent Neutral, and 23 people of 17.7 percent dissatisfied on it.

Following the table 2, it describes the proportion in each of Thailand's high school students' attitudes toward English ability. Vividly, there is only 0.8 percent of high school students who think they are well above of English average compared to other normal people. More than that, we can see it is almost 20.8 percent from all of the responders who are in the above average, as the second range. Interestingly, the highest proportion is going for the average level of using English which is 55.4 percent. Looking at the below-average part, 20 percent of High School Students opine they are on this English level. Also, there are about 3 of the percentage who chose well below average for their own option.

Table 3 : Which part of English is Thailand's high school students' weak

Choice	Frequency	Percent
Listening	16	12.3
Speaking	55	42.3
Reading	11	8.4
Writing	48	37

Table 3 demonstrates the description which part of English in high school students is weak. As the highest percentage, there is approximately 42.3 percent in terms of the figure of students who have chosen the Speaking part of English to be their weakness. Writing choice is chosen with around 37 percent while it is about 12.3 percent of high school students have chosen Listening. However, there are only 8.4% of students who have thought Reading is their trouble.

Table 3.1 : Summary of causes which make Thailand's high school students are weak in Listening skill

Reason	Inexperienced of Listening Skill (seldom do they speak with foreigner)	Misunderstanding (miss the words and variety of accent)	Uncomfortable Surroundings
Skill			
LISTENING (students)	8	5	3
% of the part	50	31.25	18.75
% of 4 skills	6.15	3.85	2.3

Table 3.1 shows Listening skills. There are 16 students who have chosen this answer, each with 3 different reasons. The first reason is an inexperienced Listening skill and has explained which seldom do they speak with a foreigner which 8 students and the percentage of this section are 50 percent. Secondly, misunderstanding of words and a variety of accents answered by 5 students which is about 31.25 percent. The last one is uncomfortable surroundings, there are 3 students who have responded that percentage of this part is 18.75 percent.

Table 3.2 : Summary of causes which make Thailand's high school students are weak in Speaking skill

Reason \ Skill	Inexperienced of Speaking Skill (seldom do they speak with foreigner)	Too afraid of Speaking (shy)	Unknowing vocabulary	Do not pay attention in class	Preference for others
SPEAKING (students)	30	15	6	2	2
% of the part	54.54	27.27	10.9	3.64	3.64
% of 4 skills	23.08	11.54	4.62	1.54	1.54

Pertaining to table 3.2, it indicates about the answers and percentage together with the figure of each cause for chosen respondents. Looking first at lacking any experience to speak English with foreigners plays a significant role in Insufficient Speaking skill with almost 30 students (54.54 percent). However, too afraid of speaking is responded by 15 students which is nearly 27.27 percent. In terms of students who have chosen the Speaking part as their weakness while the percentage of unknowing vocabulary is approximately 10.9 percent or 6 students. As for not paying attention in class tends to be the least cause of getting trouble with Speaking with around 3.64 percent that is 2 students as well as the result from preferring others to Speaking choices.

Table 3.3 : Summary of causes which make Thailand's high school students are weak in Reading skill

Reason \ Skill	Inexperienced of Reading Skill (less practice)	Unknowing vocabulary	Preference for others
READING (students)	5	4	2
% of the part	45.45	36.36	18.18
% of 4 skills	3.85	3.08	1.54

Focusing more the table 3.3 is numerical data regarding causes in which 11 high school students have chosen Reading is their weakest skill. The table shows 5 students who are less practiced in this skill or inexperienced as high as 45.45 percent. Besides, 4 students who do not know vocabulary at 36.36 percent. Interestingly, it is noticeable that only 2 students who prefer others to Reading skill at approximately 18.18 percent.

Table 3.4 : Summary of causes which make Thailand's high school students are weak in Writing skill

Reason \ Skill	Unprofessional Grammar User	Inexperienced of Writing Skill (less practice)	Do not pay attention in class	Preference for others
WRITING (students)	24	20	2	2
% of the part	50	41.67	4.17	4.17
% of 4 skills	18.46	15.38	1.54	1.54

Table 3.4 represents the Writing skill. There are 48 students who have chosen Writing, there are giving 4 different reasons. First, 24 students (50 percent) said they aren't professional grammar users. Next, 20 students (41.67 percent) chose inexperienced or less practice. Finally, third and fourth reasons are not to pay attention in class and preference for others, 2 students giving this answer which is 4.17 percent of the reason.

Table 4 : Ways to solve this problem

Choice	Frequency	Percentage
Developing themselves	55	42.3
Improve the curriculum	29	22.3
Improve the teacher skills	28	21.5
No Comment	8	6.2
More activity	6	4.6
Prevent bullying	3	2.3
Change The Prime Minister	1	0.8

Table 4 represents a number of high school students discovering ways to solve the problem. As a result, about 55 students

want to develop themselves to solve all problems. The percentage of this choice is almost half of 100%, it is 42.3 percent. Moreover, improving the curriculum is a second one with which high school students agree. There are 29 students (22.3 percent) expected to enhance the curriculum. In addition, 28 students believe teachers are the problem with the result. Improving teachers' skills is a great method while 8 persons gave no comment contemplating 6.2 percent. More activity and Prevent bullying are 6 students (4.6%) and 3 students (2.3%) in order expect to. On the other hand, one person above 0.8 percent believes changing the Prime Minister is a good process to solve the difficulty. To summarize, the questionnaire included how Thailand's high school will solve the problems in which the answer is they decide to develop themselves.

Bar chart : The reasons why Thailand's High school students are weak in English ability.

The bar chart illustrates why high school students in Thailand aren't robust in English additionally students can pick more than one answer on this question.

The first reason is Thailand's High school students are weak in grammar and vocabulary. According to the table, all students chose this cause, 53 students, accounting for 40.8% of the 130 students.

Secondly, not being assertive and teaching school personnel, from the table, all students chose this cause, 53 and 58 were 40.8 and 44.6 percent respectively. Being shy is the third choice because they are not daring to speak with native speakers and other people. Look at the table, 39 students have chosen this cause, accounting for 30 percent. Fourth, they both have very similar

percentages. Teachers take care of smart students more than students who feel less discouraged. Felt discouraged in subject matter, 29 high school students chose this cause with approximately 22.3 percent while there are about 30 students or 23.1 percent who chose prejudice. The last proportion is bullied which 27 students have chosen which accounts for 20.8 percent.

DISCUSSION

In today's status quo, most general individuals believe that the root of the failure in Thai High school students' learning English is lacking confidence to initiate a conversation with foreigners, regarding their speaking skill. Literally, grammatical range, lexical resource, and accuracy are the main causes following the outcome of the responded questionnaire. Afterward, many argue that students should have a high standard of English language skill, some need them to be good like a native.

To elucidate this view, family is the first institution for learning English since children can practice skills by making conversation with other members. Besides, the second institution is a school, not only the school has equal education, all students will right their mistakes. Not only will each student get the correct solution but also have greatly positive results due to diminishing those problems

Therefore, in this contemporary world, everything has changed, ranging from the external appearance of the world to the people's attitude toward learning new things. To elucidate this view, learning something that new and fascinating is one of the most challenging targets for someone to try and get out of their comfort zone. Moreover, we cannot use the same judgement for all of every children's future since everyone has their own personality, appearance, and also thought to desire the way they chose. Without a doubt, just because only children are shy, it does not mean that they can't improve their life.

Finally, the irrelevant factors including educational system or school teaching are not able to conclude the ability of learning English languages. Moreover, studying English, most students thought that English is difficult to learn. Based on responses from 130 students, the major reason that they are not adept in the English language is Thailand High school students' consideration of grammatical range, lexical resource, and accuracy of English is complicated which affects and makes a negative attitude to study English.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this quantitative study explores various forms of the reason for Thailand's High school students. Based on responses from 130 students from an online questionnaire, most students who have taken the questionnaire tend to be at a medium level of English, and everyone often encounters problems with speaking skills. Moreover, the first procedure to be developed in English is that students should recognize and realize the importance of self-development.

Next, the cooperation from teachers' assistants can also eventually be the most effective and best method for Thailand's High school students to reduce the conflict in English. More than that, it is accurate to say that taking care of their children's education is their priority too.

Therefore, in a questionnaire which recruited 130 Thai High school students how to find a solution. The problems which Thailand's High school students confront are caused by native language in Thailand which is not English. Actually, it is common to find some students that are not good at English in Thailand. For example, there are some which are suitable with our competency and some not, we may enable to read English but not to speak. However, if we get training and receive beneficial knowledge, we also ultimately gain the literal meaning from learning English. Finally, using inappropriately grammar as well as vocabulary is one of the influential

factors leading Thailand's High school students to have trouble with English.

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